

Synthesis and Characterization of Vanadium Pentoxide for Methane gas sensing

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Abstract

Vanadium pentoxide (V_2O_5) has drawn significant interest in the past few decades due to its various applications such as in gas sensors, thermochromic devices, optical switching devices etc. A near room temperature gas sensor is required to detect methane from coal mines, power plants and marshy areas. In the present study orthorhombic α - V_2O_5 has been synthesized by low cost and simple hydrothermal method using aqueous solution of ammonium metavanadate. The crystal structure has been identified by XRD. The presence of peaks at 146 cm^{-1} and 996 cm^{-1} in the Raman spectrum confirms the signature of V_2O_5 . FESEM images revealed the size of nanoparticles to be in the range of 30-50nm. The nanostructures showed response towards 500ppm methane gas at 100°C operating temperature.

Keywords: Vanadium pentoxide, Hydrothermal method, Methane sensing

References

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